

Coord2Region: A Python Package for Mapping 3D Brain Coordinates to Atlas Labels, Literature, and AI Summaries

Hamza Abdelhedi^{1,2,*}, Yorguin-Jose Mantilla-Ramos^{1,2,*}, Sina Esmaeili^{1,*},
Annalisa Pascarella³, Vanessa Hadid⁴, Karim Jerbi^{1,2,5}

★ These authors contributed equally.

¹ Cognitive and Computational Neuroscience Laboratory (CoCo Lab), Psychology Department,
University of Montreal, Montreal, QC, Canada

² Mila – Quebec Artificial Intelligence Institute, Montreal, QC, Canada

³ Institute for Applied Mathematics Mauro Picone, National Research Council, 00185 Rome, Italy

⁴ McGill University Health Centre (MUHC), Montreal, Quebec, Canada

⁵ UNIQUE Center (Quebec Neuro-AI Research Center), Montreal, QC, Canada

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Abstract

We present Coord2Region, an open-source Python package that streamlines coordinate-based neuroimaging workflows by automatically mapping 3D brain coordinates (e.g., MNI [9] or Talairach [17]) to anatomical regions across multiple atlases. The package links mapped coordinates to meta-analytic resources via the Neuroimaging Meta-Analysis Research Environment (NiMARE) [16], providing direct integration with Neurosynth [18] and NeuroQuery [6]. This directly connects coordinates and regions to the broader neuroimaging literature. In addition to atlas-based labeling and literature retrieval, Coord2Region offers an optional large language model (LLM) functionality that generates text summaries of linked studies and illustrative images of queried regions. These AI-assisted features are intended to support interpretation and exploration, while remaining clearly complementary to peer-reviewed literature and established neuroimaging tools. Coord2Region provides a unified pipeline with a robust command-line interface, flexible dataset management, and provider-agnostic LLM utilities, and it supports both single-coordinate and high-throughput batch queries with nearest-region fallback for volume and surface atlases. Furthermore, Coord2Region includes a web interface for interactive configuration (via JSON Schema forms) and cloud execution (via Hugging Face), enabling users to build YAML configurations and run analyses in-browser without local installation. Together, these capabilities lower friction, reduce manual errors, and improve reproducibility in coordinate-centric neuroimaging workflows, promoting more robust and transparent research practices.

1 Statement of Need

Neuroimaging studies frequently report activation locations using standardized 3D coordinates (e.g., MNI [9] or Talairach [17]). However, translating these coordinates into consistent anatomical and functional labels remains error-prone and time-consuming. GUI viewers such as MRICroGL [12, 15] and MRICron [13, 14] are excellent for interactive image exploration and rendering, but they do not

*Corresponding author: hamza.abdelhedi@umontreal.ca

support automated, programmatic coordinate-to-label mapping. Web-based viewers like NiiVue [7, 8] broaden access but likewise prioritize visualization over batch labeling. Existing tools such as Talairach Software [11] and label4MRI [3] are outdated, platform-dependent, or limited in their atlas coverage, leaving researchers to manually translate coordinates into brain regions—a practice that introduces inconsistency and undermines reproducibility. Meta-analytic toolchains such as Neurosynth and NeuroQuery bridge text and brain maps [6, 18], and NiMARE unifies modern meta-analytic methods [16], yet researchers still spend substantial time searching the literature to interpret the functional significance of reported regions. In short, there is a gap between isolated coordinates and consistent, scriptable labels enriched with literature context.

Coord2Region was created to address this gap by providing a user-friendly, automated Python tool for coordinate-to-region mapping across multiple brain atlases that also links atlas lookups to meta-analytic resources for supporting literature (Figure 1). The package offers a unified pipeline and command-line interface (CLI), multi-atlas handling, KD tree–accelerated searches, large language model (LLM)–based region summaries and images, and reproducible exports. In addition, Coord2Region provides a web interface with a JSON Schema–based configuration builder that generates valid YAML files and a cloud runner (via Streamlit) that can execute the pipeline directly in the browser, making the system usable even without local installation. Built on established open-source neuroimaging libraries (nibabel [2], Nilearn [1, 4], and MNE-Python [5, 10]) and supporting multiple LLM APIs (Gemini, OpenAI, Hugging Face), Coord2Region integrates readily into standard research workflows, reducing manual effort and errors while enabling reproducible neuroscience.

Contributions and strengths.

- **Automated anatomical labeling.** Automated anatomical region identification across more than 20 atlases, eliminating manual lookups and improving consistency across studies. *For example, a researcher with 150 fMRI activation peaks can run a single batch query and obtain standardized region names from multiple atlases in seconds.*
- **Batch processing at scale.** Efficient batch handling of large datasets of 3D coordinates. For instance, lesion coordinates from hundreds of patients can be mapped automatically without interactive software.
- **Cross-atlas robustness.** Atlas-agnostic, KD-tree–accelerated nearest-region fallback (for both volume and surface atlases), ensuring that every coordinate receives a label while reporting distances to support interpretation of uncertainty.
- **Literature linkage.** Integration with Neurosynth and NeuroQuery via NiMARE [6, 16, 18], linking atlas-defined regions directly to more than 20,000 published functional neuroimaging studies. *For example, a coordinate in the left inferior frontal gyrus can be associated with studies reporting its role in language processing.*
- **Optional LLM utilities.** Provider-agnostic LLM utilities (synchronous, asynchronous, and streaming) for generating text summaries of linked studies and illustrative images of queried regions. These outputs are explicitly positioned as aids to interpretation, not replacements for systematic review.
- **Unified access modes.** A single `run_pipeline` API and CLI that implement the full coordinates→atlas→literature→AI-summary workflow. All functionality is exposed through

Coord2Region Workflow & Integrations

Figure 1: **Coord2Region workflow and integrations.** Users provide **MNI/Talairach coordinates** (single or **batch**) or **region name(s)**. Coordinates are mapped to standardized labels across **20+ atlases**; when a point falls outside a parcel or near boundaries, an **atlas-agnostic nearest-region fallback** assigns the closest region (KD-tree accelerated for volume and surface atlases) and can report distances to support uncertainty interpretation. Mapped regions are then linked (via **NiMARE**) to **NeuroQuery** and **Neurosynth**, connecting labels to **20k+ functional neuroimaging studies**. Optional, provider-agnostic LLM utilities generate brief summaries of linked studies, and the workflow can produce lightweight region visualizations. Results are exportable (e.g., **CSV/JSON/PDF**) and runnable through a unified **Python API, CLI, or web interface** for configuration building and cloud execution.

the Python API, a command-line interface, and a reproducible YAML configuration system, enabling use by both developers and non-programmers.

- **Web interface.** A web interface for building configuration files, generating CLI commands from user-specified inputs, outputs, and options, and a cloud runner (via Streamlit / Hugging Face) that executes the end-to-end workflow in the browser.
- **Flexible applications.** Flexible usage across modalities and paradigms, including fMRI, EEG/MEG source localization, lesion mapping, and intracranial electrode studies.
- **Open science practices.** Open-source and actively maintained on GitHub, with a community-driven development model that welcomes contributions, alongside rich documentation, examples, and unit tests to support reproducible use and extension.

2 Methods

2.1 Overview

Coord2Region adopts a modular architecture designed for flexibility, maintainability, and ease of extension. Each module fulfills a distinct role, yet the components can be composed into a unified pipeline. Given (a) one or more coordinates or (b) a region name, the pipeline executes the following steps:

- M1. Data initialization.** Resolve directories, load available atlases, precompute centroids, build KD-trees, and load metadata. This initialization ensures that subsequent mapping steps are efficient and reproducible. *Example: when running multiple queries in a session, atlas files are loaded once and cached for reuse, reducing runtime from minutes to seconds.*
- M2. Coordinate-to-region mapping.** Translate input coordinates into anatomical labels using `AtlasMapper` or `MultiAtlasMapper`. If a coordinate falls outside labeled regions, a nearest-region search is performed using prebuilt KD-trees, and the Euclidean distance to the nearest voxel or vertex is reported. *Example: a peak activation at $(-42, -22, 8)$ can be mapped to “left inferior frontal gyrus,” with a 2.3 mm distance to the nearest atlas voxel.*
- M3. Study retrieval.** Retrieve studies around a coordinate x within radius r or by region label using NiMARE-backed datasets (Neurosynth / NeuroQuery) with CrossRef / PubMed metadata fill. *Example: the same inferior frontal gyrus coordinate can return dozens of linked studies, including work on language processing and cognitive control.*
- M4. Summarization and visualization (optional).** Use LLMs via `AIModelInterface` (a provider-agnostic wrapper) for generating text summaries of linked studies and optional AI-based images of queried regions. Coord2Region can also produce atlas overlays for MNI coordinates with watermarking. These features help researchers rapidly contextualize results, while remaining clearly complementary to systematic literature review.
- M5. Export.** Save results in multiple formats (JSON, CSV, PDF, pickle, or directory trees), ensuring compatibility with downstream analyses and facilitating reproducibility.

2.2 Atlas mapping

This component forms the core of Coord2Region.

`AtlasFetcher` & `AtlasFileHandler`. classes handle retrieval and I/O for brain atlas datasets, supporting downloads from online repositories and loading from local files (e.g., NIfTI `.nii/.nii.gz`, NumPy `.npz`). Together, they streamline atlas management and enable rapid integration of new atlases, improving scalability and usability. *Practical use:* a researcher can download and register multiple atlases (e.g., AAL, Harvard–Oxford, Destrieux) in a single call and apply them across the same dataset.

`AtlasMapper`, `MultiAtlasMapper`, `BatchAtlasMapper`. These core classes perform coordinate-to-region mapping, with complementary scopes:

- `AtlasMapper`: mapping between coordinates and anatomical labels for a *single* atlas.
- `MultiAtlasMapper`: coordinated mapping across *multiple* atlases, returning per-atlas labels and facilitating cross-atlas comparison.

- **BatchAtlasMapper**: high-throughput processing of *sets* of coordinates (e.g., many participants or conditions), wrapping the previous mappers with batching, caching, and progress reporting.

All three support single points or large batches; convert bidirectionally between coordinates, voxel indices, and region labels; and automatically infer hemisphere from region labels. *Example: 500 lesion coordinates can be batch-processed across AAL and Destrieux in one query, with outputs labeled consistently.*

Edge cases are resolved via nearest-neighbor interpolation so coordinates that do not overlap labeled voxels map to the nearest anatomical region. For volume atlases, we precompute the set of labeled voxels $V \subset \mathbb{Z}^3$ and build a KD-tree over their MNI coordinates. Given an input location x , if x is unlabeled we return the label at

$$v^* = \arg \min_{v \in V} \|x - \text{mni}(v)\|_2$$

and report the distance

$$d = \|x - \text{mni}(v^*)\|_2.$$

For surface atlases, we index labeled vertices and build a KD-tree over their 3D positions; for vertex-to-triangle ambiguities, we prefer the smallest geodesic distance when available, otherwise the Euclidean distance. KD-trees, centroids, and label maps are cached in a user-configurable directory and serialized for reuse (batch API/CLI), enabling large-scale, cross-atlas mapping on standard hardware.

2.3 Datasets (Neurosynth & NeuroQuery) and Study Search

Through `fetch_datasets`, `deduplicate_datasets`, and `search_studies`, `Coord2Region` provides a NiMARE-backed integration with large-scale meta-analytic resources (Neurosynth, NeuroQuery). This module links atlas-derived coordinates or region labels to relevant published studies and associated cognitive terms. *Example: a researcher entering coordinates in the posterior cingulate cortex receives a curated list of studies relating this region to memory and default mode network activity, with DOIs and abstracts included when available.*

Missing bibliographic fields (e.g., DOI, journal, abstract) are automatically backfilled from PubMed and CrossRef. The resulting standardized study records include identifiers (PMID and/or DOI when available), titles, abstracts, and the source dataset, spanning more than 14,000 articles via Neurosynth and 13,000 via NeuroQuery. Cross-source deduplication ensures that overlapping entries are merged into a unique study set—for instance, if both datasets return the same hippocampal study, it is listed only once, reducing redundancy in literature searches.

By tying anatomical results directly to the literature, this module enables rapid functional interpretation and efficient study discovery. All outputs can be exported to JSON or CSV for downstream meta-analysis, integration into custom pipelines, or sharing with collaborators.

2.4 LLM utilities

`AIModelInterface` provides a unified wrapper for multiple LLM providers (OpenAI, Anthropic, Google Gemini, OpenRouter, Hugging Face). It implements robust retries with backoff and timeouts, asynchronous batch generation, token-aware streaming, an extensible library of prompt templates (with support for user-defined templates), and LRU caching to avoid redundant calls. For figures, it can compose MNI-space overlays with AI-generated region sketches and apply watermarking.

The API accepts single or batched inputs (coordinates or region labels) and returns structured outputs (e.g., JSON, CSV) and LaTeX-ready text. This module standardizes narrative reporting (summaries, captions, methods blurbs) across studies, reduces manual literature-synthesis effort, and scales to large datasets. Caching and templating improve reproducibility and consistency across runs and providers, while asynchronous and streaming modes shorten end-to-end pipelines and simplify integration in notebooks, scripts, and the CLI.

2.5 Pipeline and CLI commands

Coord2Region supports multiple usage levels to accommodate users with different technical backgrounds. At the lowest level, users may directly call individual functions (e.g., `mni_to_region_name`, `get_studies_for_coordinates`, `generate_summary`) to build custom workflows. *Example: a methods developer can script a pipeline that maps 300 MNI coordinates to AAL atlas regions, retrieves associated literature, and saves the results as a CSV for meta-analysis.*

For higher-level use, the Pipeline API (in `pipeline.py`) chains the key processing steps—coordinate mapping, dataset fetching and deduplication, study retrieval, image generation, and summarization—into a single coherent workflow that returns consistent outputs (region names, study lists, images, summaries). Alternatively, the command-line interface (CLI in `cli.py`) exposes the same functionality via commands such as `coords-to-summary`, `coords-to-image`, `coords-to-insights`, `region-to-insights` and `coords-to-study`, and can optionally consume YAML configuration files to facilitate reproducible execution and sharing of workflows.

Users can therefore choose to work purely in Python code, via the high-level pipeline API, or through the CLI (with or without YAML), and can transition between modes as their needs evolve. This tiered design ensures accessibility for a wide range of researchers, from developers building advanced pipelines to clinical scientists seeking quick coordinate-to-region mappings.

Figure 2 illustrates the architecture and data flow of the Coord2Region pipeline. The process begins when the user supplies either atlas names or 3D coordinates as input. The `AtlasFetcher` component first retrieves or lists available atlases. Next, `AtlasMapper` (or its `BatchAtlasMapper` / `MultiAtlasMapper` variants) converts between MNI coordinates and region names, computes distances to centroids or labeled voxels, and performs system conversions as needed. Once mapping is complete, the system loads cached data or fetches datasets, deduplicates overlapping entries, and `get_studies_for_coordinates` retrieves a list of relevant studies for each coordinate.

In parallel, the user’s selection of image or summary models and prompt templates is passed to `AIModelInterface`, which wraps methods such as `generate_text` and `generate_image`. The pipeline invokes `generate_region_image` to produce approximate visual representations of mapped regions and `generate_summary` to synthesize textual summaries based on the retrieved study lists. The final outputs include region names, study lists per coordinate, approximate region images, and study summaries. When region names are provided instead of coordinates, the workflow is analogous, with the restriction that a single atlas is used.

The label “Batch/Multi*” in the `AtlasMapper` block denotes that `BatchAtlasMapper` (for handling multiple coordinates) and `MultiAtlasMapper` (for handling multiple atlases) are supported; both extend or wrap the base `AtlasMapper` and are omitted from the diagram for clarity. Additional classes, utilities, error-handling, and caching modules exist in the full implementation but are not shown.

Example output. To illustrate the end-to-end behavior of `coords-to-insights`, we ran the command below on two input coordinates using the Harvard–Oxford atlas and three evidence sources (`neurosynth`, `neuroquery`, `nidm_pain`). The tool (i) maps each coordinate to an atlas region label, (ii) retrieves supporting studies, and (iii) generates a structured JSON report together

Figure 2: **Overview of the core functionalities workflow.** The pipeline starts with user-provided inputs (blue), such as atlas names, 3D coordinates, or model specifications. Core functions (yellow) orchestrate data retrieval, mapping, and analysis, relying on dedicated classes (green) like `AtlasFetcher`, `AtlasMapper (Batch/Multi*)`, and `AIModelInterface`. Internal data flow and dependencies are shown with dashed red arrows, while external inputs and outputs follow solid black and red connections. The system produces outputs (pink), including mapped region names, study summaries, and approximate images. In the case where region names are provided as input, the workflow is similar but restricted to a single atlas. The “Batch/Multi*” label indicates the existence of `BatchAtlasMapper` (handling multiple coordinates simultaneously) and `MultiAtlasMapper` (using multiple atlases at once); both build on `AtlasMapper` but are omitted for simplicity.

with optional visual outputs. Figure 3 shows the corresponding images (AI illustration and Nilearn overlay for each coordinate), while the listings provide the exact CLI invocation, a representative console log excerpt, and a trimmed JSON excerpt capturing the main fields returned by the pipeline.

Example CLI call.

```

coord2region coords-to-insights 14 -56 -7 -8.8 -95.5 17 \
--openai-api-key <OPENAI_API_KEY> \
--sources 'neurosynth,neuroquery,nidm_pain' \
--atlas harvard-oxford \
--image-backend both \
--image-model dall-e-3 \
--image-prompt-type anatomical \

```

```
--summary_models gpt-4o \  
--study_search_radius '5' \  
--region_search_radius: 0.4 \  
--prompt_type summary \  
--summary_models gpt-4o \  
--summary_max_tokens: 1000
```

Console output (excerpt).

```
INFO:coord2region.coord2study:Loaded deduplicated dataset with 19169 studies ...  
[fetch_atlas_harvard_oxford] Dataset found in ../nilearn_data/fsl  
INFO:httpx:HTTP Request: POST https://api.openai.com/v1/responses "HTTP/1.1 200 OK"  
INFO:httpx:HTTP Request: POST https://api.openai.com/v1/images/generations "HTTP/1.1 200 OK"  
INFO:root:Processed 2/2 inputs
```

Structured result (trimmed JSON excerpt).

```
[  
  {  
    "coordinate": [20.0, -12.0, 10.0],  
    "region_labels": {"harvard-oxford": "Central Opercular Cortex"},  
    "studies": [{"id": "19874897-1", "title": "Shared neural resources between left and right  
interlimb coordination skills: the neural substrate of abstract motor representations."}],  
    "images": {"ai": "figures/example_coord1_ai.png",  
              "nilearn": "figures/example_coord1_nilearn.png"},  
    "summary": "The MNI coordinate [20.00, -12.00, 10.00] is situated within the Central Opercular  
Cortex, an area that plays a crucial role in integrating sensory, motor, and cognitive  
functions. This region is particularly significant for its involvement in various aspects  
of sensorimotor processing and coordination, as evidenced by its activation during tasks  
requiring interlimb coordination skills.\n\nResearch indicates that activation in the  
Central Opercular Cortex is frequently linked to the execution and planning of complex  
motor tasks, highlighting its role in formulating abstract motor representations. This  
function is particularly pertinent in studies exploring the neural underpinnings of  
interlimb coordination, wherein participants must integrate feedback from different body  
parts to perform synchronized movements. The central opercular cortex's positioning allows  
it to act as a hub that facilitates communication between sensory input and motor output,  
underscoring its importance in tasks that require fluid and coordinated response to dynamic  
stimuli.\n\nIn experimental contexts, this region has been implicated in various  
conditions, such as those involving rhythmic motor tasks or lateralized movement paradigms.  
The activation observed at this coordinate typically emerges during tasks that necessitate  
a high degree of motor precision and coordination, suggesting that it might serve a  
broader role in motor control beyond the interlimb coordination specifically. \n\nDespite a  
growing consensus on the significance of the Central Opercular Cortex in motor functions,  
debates persist regarding the extent of its involvement in cognitive versus purely motor  
tasks. Some studies propose that this area may also contribute to higher-order processes,  
such as decision-making during movement, highlighting an interface between cognitive  
processes and motor execution. This notion invites further examination of the cognitive  
dimensions of movement, suggesting that regions traditionally regarded as motor may also  
support complex cognitive operations.\n\nOverall, the findings associated with the MNI  
coordinate [20.00, -12.00, 10.00] highlight the Central Opercular Cortex as a vital region  
for both motor coordination and the cognitive processes that underpin it, supporting a  
multifaceted understanding of how our brains facilitate skilled movement."  
  },  
  {  
    "coordinate": [38.0, -48.0, 49.0],  
    "region_labels": {"harvard-oxford": "Superior Parietal Lobule"},  
    "studies": [{"id": "9065511-1", "title": "Environmental knowledge is subserved by separable  
dorsal/ventral neural areas."}],  
    "images": {"ai": "figures/example_coord2_ai.png",
```

```

    "nilearn": "figures/example_coord2_nilearn.png"},
  "summary": "The MNI coordinate [38.00, -48.00, 49.00] is located within the superior parietal
    lobule, an anatomically and functionally significant region of the brain. This area is
    nestled within the parietal lobe, situated superiorly and posteriorly to the intraparietal
    sulcus, and is involved in a variety of complex cognitive processes.\n\n### Anatomical
    Significance\nThe superior parietal lobule is known for its role in integrating sensory
    information and is associated with both visual and spatial processing. It acts as a
    crossroads for information from multiple sensory modalities, contributing to our
    understanding of spatial awareness and the manipulation of objects in our environment.\n\n
    ### Functional Roles\nActivation in this region has been linked to several cognitive
    functions, prominently including spatial awareness, attention, and the processing of
    environmental knowledge. Its involvement in dorsal and ventral processing streams suggests
    a specialization in higher-order cognitive strategies relevant for navigating and
    understanding the surrounding world. Specifically, environmental knowledge\u2014how we
    learn about and relate to the spaces and items in our environment\u2014can be traced to
    activity within this parietal region. The studies suggest that this area may facilitate
    both the practical and conceptual aspects of spatial awareness, connecting perceptual
    stimuli with stored knowledge and actions.\n\n### Experimental Contexts\nActivation at this
    coordinate has been reported in studies examining various tasks involving spatial
    cognition and environmental interactions. Although the specific tasks employed in pertinent
    studies may vary, they generally encompass scenarios where spatial manipulation, visual
    attention, or knowledge application is required. For instance, the study linking
    environmental knowledge to the dorsal and ventral neural areas suggests that such cognitive
    demands evoke activation in the superior parietal lobule, emphasizing the region's
    involvement in tasks that require participants to integrate sensory inputs for effective
    navigation and task performance.\n\n### Patterns and Debates\nWhile the findings
    demonstrate consistent activation of the superior parietal lobule with respect to spatial
    and environmental cognition, debates may arise concerning the specific contributions of
    neighboring structures to this activation. Questions persist about whether the observed
    effects are solely attributable to the superior parietal lobule or if contributions from
    adjacent cortical areas, like the intraparietal sulcus or the precuneus, play a role. Thus,
    while the superior parietal lobule is undoubtedly a critical player in the cognitive
    processes tied to the coordinate in question, the intricate interplay with surrounding
    regions remains an area of ongoing research and debate.\n\nThis synthesis highlights the
    importance of the superior parietal lobule in spatial and environmental cognition,
    revealing a complex landscape where anatomical structure and function intersect to
    facilitate our interaction with the world around us."
  }
]

```

3 Web Interface: Config Builder and Cloud Runner

Coord2Region also offers a fully functional **web interface**¹(Figure 4) that lowers the barrier to entry for non-programmers and supports reproducible workflows directly in the browser. At the heart of this interface is the *Config Builder*, which is powered by JSON Schema-driven forms and presents users with dynamic fields for specifying input mode (coordinates or region names), atlas selection, data sources, output options (studies, summaries, images), and model or prompt parameters.

The Config Builder guides users through the following steps:

1. Enter coordinates (single or batch) or region names.
2. Select one or more atlases (e.g., AAL, Harvard–Oxford, Destrieux).

¹<https://babasanfour.github.io/Coord2Region/>

3. Choose desired outputs such as anatomical labels, linked studies, summaries, or images.
4. Configure model and output options (e.g., number of studies retrieved, whether to generate summaries, output formats).

(a) Nilearn overlay (Central Opercular Cortex).

(b) Nilearn overlay (Superior Parietal Lobule).

(c) AI illustration (Central Opercular Cortex).

(d) AI illustration (Superior Parietal Lobule).

Figure 3: Example outputs from `coord2region coords-to-insights` for two input coordinates. For each coordinate, `Coord2Region` generates (i) an atlas overlay (Nilearn) and (ii) an optional AI illustration, alongside mapped labels, retrieved studies, and a text summary.

As users complete the form, live validation ensures that only configurations consistent with the underlying schema are allowed. The interface also displays a live YAML preview and a corresponding CLI command snippet, enabling users to download the YAML, copy the command, or directly invoke CLI execution based on their selections.

Complementing the Config Builder is the *Cloud Runner*, a Streamlit-based web app (e.g., deployed via Hugging Face Spaces) that wraps the full `Coord2Region` pipeline. Users can submit inputs, choose atlases and options, and run mapping, study retrieval, summarization, and image generation entirely in the browser, without requiring a local installation. Because the `Cloud Runner` uses the same core logic as the CLI and pipeline, results remain consistent across interfaces. The current Web Runner, hosted on Hugging Face Spaces, is intended as a demonstration environment and

supports single-coordinate or small-scale queries; high-throughput runs should use the local CLI and Python interfaces.

Together, the Config Builder and Cloud Runner enable a seamless, end-to-end web experience: users can interactively build valid YAML configurations, execute analyses in the cloud, and, if desired, transition to CLI or Python usage using the same configuration files. The schema-driven design ensures that any future additions to configuration options are automatically reflected in the web UI, keeping all modes in sync with minimal maintenance.

4 Discussion

Coord2Region addresses a central bottleneck in coordinate-based neuroimaging: translating 3D coordinates into consistent anatomical labels with direct links to supporting literature. Widely used visualization tools (e.g., MRICroGL, NiiVue) and meta-analytic platforms (e.g., Neurosynth, NeuroQuery, NiMARE) provide powerful capabilities, but none offer a unified workflow that integrates atlas-based labeling, study retrieval, and automated summaries.

Compared with manual coordinate lookups in GUI software, Coord2Region offers:

- **Speed and scalability.** Large datasets of hundreds or thousands of coordinates can be batch-processed within minutes using KD-tree acceleration and caching.
- **Consistency.** Multi-atlas queries ensure that results are reproducible and comparable across studies, with explicit reporting of nearest-region distances for ambiguous cases.
- **Literature integration.** Direct links to peer-reviewed publications reduce the time spent manually searching PubMed or Google Scholar for functional interpretation.

Compared with meta-analytic frameworks alone, Coord2Region fills the “glue layer” by providing coordinate-level entry points. A researcher can start with a single activation peak or lesion coordinate and quickly move to literature-backed summaries without needing full statistical maps. The inclusion of LLM-powered summaries and illustrative images extends this pipeline by offering optional interpretive aids. These outputs are not intended to replace systematic review, but instead provide a useful first-pass synthesis, particularly in exploratory or clinical contexts. *For example, a clinician localizing electrode sites may use the AI-generated summary to obtain a quick overview of cognitive functions associated with a mapped region before examining the primary literature in detail.*

Overall, Coord2Region complements existing visualization and meta-analytic ecosystems by serving as an automation and reproducibility layer. It lowers the barrier to consistent coordinate labeling, accelerates functional interpretation, and reduces human error, while maintaining compatibility with established neuroimaging libraries (nibabel, Nilearn, MNE-Python) and databases (Neurosynth, NeuroQuery, NiMARE).

Beyond its Python API, Coord2Region is deliberately designed to be accessible to users with little or no programming experience. The web-based Config Builder and Cloud Runner provide a point-and-click interface for defining, running, and sharing analyses. By exposing all key options—input mode, atlas selection, output types, and model parameters—through JSON Schema-driven forms, the web interface allows users to construct valid configurations without writing code or editing YAML manually. Live validation and immediate YAML/CLI previews further reduce errors and support transparent reporting.

Similarly, the command-line interface offers a low-friction entry point for non-programmers who are comfortable running simple terminal commands. High-level commands (e.g., `coords-to-summary`,

Figure 4: Coord2Region web interface workflow. Users begin by providing input (e.g., coordinates or region names) in Step 1, then choose the desired output type (Step 2). In Step 3 they specify atlas and output settings, and in Step 4 configure output-related parameters. The live YAML preview updates as settings change (Step 5), after which the user can either copy a CLI command or download a YAML configuration (Step 6). Finally (Step 7), the user pastes or uploads the YAML into the Cloud Runner interface, supplies any remaining inputs, and runs the pipeline in the browser.

`coords-to-study`, `coords-to-insights`) encapsulate the full pipeline behind a small set of arguments, and YAML configuration files can be reused across machines, projects, and collaborators. Together, the web interface and CLI make it possible for students, clinicians, and other domain experts to benefit from automated atlas labeling and literature linkage without needing to develop custom Python scripts, while still remaining fully compatible with more advanced, code-centric workflows.

Future work will extend the package with probabilistic atlases, M/EEG sensor support, and automated integration of new literature as it becomes available. By situating coordinate mapping within a reproducible, scriptable, and literature-linked workflow, `Coord2Region` supports more reliable and transparent reporting in neuroimaging research.

5 Reproducibility & Availability

Open source and licensing. `Coord2Region` is open source and developed publicly on GitHub. Issues, discussions, examples, and continuous-integration (CI) logs are available to support transparent development and community review. The project welcomes external contributions via standard pull-request workflows, with coding style and contribution guidelines documented in the repository.

Core dependencies. The package targets Python ≥ 3.10 and relies on widely adopted scientific libraries: `numpy`, `scipy`, `pandas`, `nibabel`, `nilearn`, and (for surface workflows) `MNE-Python`. The command-line interface is implemented using `argparse` and standard library modules.

Optional integrations. For literature retrieval and decoding, `Coord2Region` interoperates with `NiMARE` and its supported resources (e.g., `Neurosynth`, `NeuroQuery`). LLM-powered summaries and image synthesis are optional features enabled via provider-specific Python packages (e.g., `OpenAI`, `Anthropic`, `Google Gemini`, `OpenRouter SDKs`, or local `Hugging Face` backends). These integrations are isolated behind the `AIModelInterface`, so that core atlas mapping remains provider-agnostic and usable without any AI keys.

Determinism and caching. Atlas volumes, surface annotations, centroids, and KD-trees are cached under a user-configurable data directory to accelerate repeated runs. Package and atlas versions are recorded in outputs, and random seeds are fixed where applicable. All pipeline steps can export machine-readable artifacts (JSON/CSV) alongside human-readable reports (PDF) to support reuse, inspection, and audit.

Reproducible interfaces. Every capability available in Python is mirrored in the `coord2region` CLI (e.g., `coords-to-atlas`, `coords-to-summary`, `coords-to-insights`, `region-to-coords`), enabling both scripted and interactive use. Examples demonstrate end-to-end calls, expected inputs/outputs, and how to pin software and data versions for long-term reproducibility.

Data and third-party resources. When fetching atlases or meta-analytic datasets, the package preserves original licenses and citation information. Users are encouraged to cite the relevant atlas and dataset sources when publishing results. Installation instructions, minimal examples, and CI status badges are linked from the README and the online documentation.

6 Limitations

Atlas choice and resolution inherently influence derived labels; surface/volume mismatches can introduce edge effects and partial-volume artifacts. Nearest-region fallbacks introduce distance-dependent uncertainty, so `Coord2Region` reports distances and allows user-defined thresholds to flag or exclude low-confidence labels. LLM-based summaries may reflect provider biases, incomplete coverage of the literature, and model drift over time; to mitigate this, we record provenance (model

name, version, prompts) and support offline or local models when available. Users should avoid over-interpreting labels as precise neuroanatomical ground truth, should treat AI-generated text and images as heuristic aids rather than definitive evidence, and must respect dataset licenses, citation requirements, and human-subjects constraints when using or sharing results.

7 Future Directions

Coord2Region actively encourages community participation and future enhancements. Current priorities for ongoing development include:

- **Richer visualization.** Integrating more interactive views of coordinate mappings onto brain surfaces and volumes (e.g., web-based 3D viewers, hoverable annotations, montage exports).
- **Expanded atlas and modality support.** Adding probabilistic and functional atlases, improved handling of subject-specific spaces, and first-class support for M/EEG sensor and source-space coordinates.
- **Enhanced AI workflows.** Incorporating more robust prompting strategies, support for retrieval-augmented LLM summaries grounded in the fetched literature, and tools for systematically comparing outputs across models.
- **Automated literature updates.** Streamlining periodic refresh of meta-analytic datasets and bibliographic metadata so that coordinate-to-literature mappings remain current as new studies are published.

The project welcomes contributions in the form of new atlases, additional example notebooks, improvements to documentation, bug reports, feature requests, and pull requests implementing new functionality. Community feedback will guide the prioritization of future features and integrations.

8 Documentation and Package Repository

For further information, detailed guidelines, and usage examples, users can consult the online documentation at <https://coord2region.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> and explore the package repository at <https://github.com/BabaSanfour/Coord2Region> for source code, issue tracking, and collaborative development. These resources are continuously updated to support and enhance the user experience, including tutorials, API reference, and release notes.

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